

ORGANIZATION OF ENGLISH SPEECH ETIQUETTE

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Annotation

In order to fully understand the tasks, significance, and places of their use of speech etiquette units, it is necessary to use the theoretical conclusions of sociolinguistics, paralinguistics, and linguopragmatics related to speech etiquette.

The importance of speech culture is so important that it is observed at all levels, starting from the words of children and adults, ending with business communication and even street conversation. Naturally, these will be different formulas. The main function of speech etiquette is communicative.

Key words: speech etiquette , forms of communication, Uzbek and English cultures, communicative behaviour.

As in any nation, English has its own forms of communication, and the scientific study of its linguistic aspects dates back to antiquity. English and Uzbek are structurally different. Uzbek is a synthetic language, so polite forms are represented by prefixes, infixes or suffixes, and in English different expressions are used, please (if you don't mind) I would like / I'll like and so on.

From the point of view of intercultural communication, it is important to take into account the differences between Uzbek and English cultures in the process of mastering the rules of English speech etiquette. It allows students to understand the speech culture of these people through the communicative behaviour of Uzbeks, to compare and find similarities and differences in customs and traditions, to increase interest in their own culture, and to explore ethnic and cultural heritage.

The following main tasks are solved in the teaching of communication: When studying the rules of speech etiquette, students should have the following: ability to use them in light conditions; existing methods of "expanding" polite formulas; the ability to express kindness with emphasis on facial expressions, gestures, and other nonverbal means.

In Uzbek, there are two types of pronouns in the second person: singular unofficial "you" and official "you". In addition, there are gentle formulas for asking the person sitting at the table to taste the food, such as "Take" or "Please",

which in English is equivalent to "help yourself" - . Thank you. "There is no word for reporter in English, but "thank you" is correct.

When we asked someone else to give us a book, we said, "Can you give me a book?"

Please, polite answer (here you are).

"Who is this?" when we asked. In English, "Do you know this person?" - "Who is this person?" There are many words in Uzbek language used in official speech, there are communicative etiquette - "Forgive me" - "Excuse me", "If you allow me?" - "Will you allow me?", "Welcome" - "My pleasure" and etc. In teaching the rules of speech etiquette, we need to draw students' attention to the peculiarities of the English and Uzbek grammatical systems. English and Uzbek are structurally different. Uzbek is a synthetic language, so polite forms are represented in a word by prefixes, affixes or suffixes, while in English different expressions are used.

According to Grice, politeness is one of the most important principles in teaching English etiquette. The principle of politeness is mainly implemented in the actions of interrogative speech. An inquiry form is often used as a reliable way to implement the principle of politeness as an expression of communicative intent. In an English-speaking and Uzbek-speaking society, communication between cultured people takes place on three levels of politeness - formal, neutral, and familiar. The specific style of speech is appropriate for each level of politeness. Formal courtesy is the norm in institutions, organizations, businesses, education, health care, services, and so on. The social conditionality of the interlocutors' behaviors, actions, and intentions is expressed in the style of their verbal behavior. Deviation from the level of formal politeness in a formal situation is perceived as blatant disrespect to the interlocutor and can lead the interlocutor to conflict and even the severance of a formal relationship.

However, the above interpretations do not fully explain the concept of culture. Culture can be considered as one of the highest forms of all aspects of life. Beginning in the 1970s, a number of countries around the world, and especially the United Kingdom, began to experience dramatic changes in people's worldviews as a result of their understanding of culture.

Specificity of speech etiquette and intercultural differences create the need to learn from the very essence of communication. Intercultural communication is not only linguistic, but also begins with the appearance, facial expressions, gestures and gestures.

Grice highlights three aspects of communication:

1. Communicative communication, 2. Attractiveness, 3. Self-expression. While Grice fully endorses this view, it should be noted that mutual respect also plays an important role in speech etiquette.

Problems of intercultural communication are reflected in food, language, art, music, clothing, values, traditions, and needs. Intercultural problems can be likened to an iceberg. Grice said that if the speakers and listeners have the same cultural background, they can easily understand each other, and if the speakers and listeners have different cultural backgrounds, they can have mutual speech problems. In solving speech problems, questions and answers, feedback and rational analysis play an important role in resolving misunderstandings. Additional comments are also available here.

Any aspect of one's speech etiquette that is not part of one's speech etiquette is considered alien. It follows that the term alien is always subjective and relative in nature.

Because everyone living in the world, including the UK, has rights and freedoms in speech etiquette, religious and cultural relations.

Article 18 of Chapter V of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "In the Republic of Uzbekistan, all citizens have the same rights and freedoms, regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, beliefs, personal and social status. They are equal before the law. Privileges shall be determined only by law and shall be in accordance with the principles of social justice." No state can impede these freedoms.

Intercultural communication can also take place in business trips abroad, work and study, or international business contacts. Of course, every immigrant who wants to immigrate to another country must learn the values, norms, etiquette, and code of conduct of that country. This will prevent intercultural conflicts and facilitate the process of integration into the country. Immigrants must respect the customs and values of that country while preserving their values and traditions. Today, the term multiculturalism is widely used in European countries. The definition of a multicultural society refers to the fact that lifestyles are made up of different cultures.

There are three types of multicultural society. In the first round, society is statistically multicultural, but in practice it is monocultural. At the same time, members of relatively superior societies formally promote their culture everywhere, while members of minority cultures live only in a narrow range of relationships.

The second type of multiculturalism (multiculturalism) is widespread, in which the culture established by the indigenous people is to some extent dominant, while members of other cultures strive to preserve their cultural identity. Today, invitations are used in the UK and Uzbekistan.

If the number of guests is more than 15-20 people, the invitation should be sent at least two weeks in advance. The official invitation states that the request = Invitation requires an answer (r.i.r = request is requested) / from the invitation of the British Embassy /. Applicants must provide a response on whether or not to attend at least one week before the date of the invitation. Because the inviter may have time to invite someone other than friends or acquaintances. If the invited guest is a couple, the name and surname of both of them should be written on the invitation.

If the offer is on Sunday, it means you don't have to go there in formal clothes. Given that he is not familiar with the customs, the invitees may write "casual" on the invitation at the invitation of the British Embassy. This means that you don't have to wear a formal dress or a tie.

The invitation should not be officially marked with the names John and Elisa, but simply Mr. and Mrs. The Adams. But if one of them, for example, does not know the name of his wife well, cannot be written as Mrs. John Adams and Mrs. Adams. This is against the rules of etiquette.

Time is of the essence in English etiquette. The guest must arrive on time. The late arrival of the guest interferes with the course of the event, and the early arrival hinders the preparation process. It is rude for a guest to be late for a hot meal for thirty minutes. When that happens, he may apologize.

For example, I therefore apologize for my delay and for the fact that my explanation on this matter has been incorporated into one.

Today, a number of countries around the world are multicultural, and for the peaceful coexistence of the people of these countries, a thorough study of the normative interaction between people, the peculiarities of speech more relevant. In order to prevent intercultural conflicts, people are required to thoroughly study and respect the customs and values of the peoples of that country, while preserving their values and traditions. Forms of communication were first studied as didactic and cultural issues, but later the participation of linguistic units in these processes and their importance became the object of research in the field of linguistics.

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